

Belt and Road: China's Plan for Global Control

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China's Expanding Influence

In the past decade, China has expanded its influence and presence throughout the African continent. Through the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) most notably, China has sought to economically develop Africa by supporting the construction of key infrastructure that aims to bring the continent into the 21st century. Reports of recent years, however, challenge the lighthearted narrative of the Chinese Communist Party (CCP), leaving many to wonder if China has become Africa's new colonizer.

The Belt and Road Initiative: A Double-Edged Sword

In 2013, Chinese President Xi Jinping announced the BRI for the stated purpose of removing “the biggest bottleneck to Africa's development”, being infrastructure.¹ While a global initiative, with partnerships spanning Latin America, the Indo-Pacific, and even Europe, Africa has been targeted. Over \$700 billion has since been invested in modern highways, railroads, hydroelectric plants and more by Chinese state-owned construction companies, leaving opinions among the global West, supporters of the CCP, and optimistic Africans split in a blend of shock, joy, and fear globally.²³

The mixed reaction is a result of a successful messaging campaign by the CCP that its goals to overthrow the West and economically develop each other after colonialism are shared.⁴ The African Union Representative to China Rahamtalla M. Osman reinforced this claim,

¹ CNBC, “China's President Xi Jinping on Belt and Road Initiative in Africa,” *CNBC*, September 3, 2018, <https://www.cnbc.com/2018/09/03/chinas-president-xi-jinping-on-belt-and-road-initiative-in-africa.html>.

² VOA News, “Key Chinese Belt and Road Projects Underway in Africa,” *Voice of America*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.voanews.com/a/key-chinese-belt-and-road-projects-underway-in-africa/7767507.html>.

³ Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, “How Are Various Countries Responding to China's Belt and Road Initiative?,” *Carnegie Endowment for International Peace*, April 2019, <https://carnegieendowment.org/posts/2019/04/how-are-various-countries-responding-to-chinas-belt-and-road-initiative?lang=en>.

⁴ Rush Doshi, “The Long Game: China's Grand Strategy to Displace American Order,” *Brookings Institution*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/the-long-game-chinas-grand-strategy-to-displace-american-order/>.

with a 2023 report by the Chinese state-owned news blog PR Newswire quoting Osman as saying that the BRI is “a win-win cooperation, not a charity”.⁵

Across the continent, there are many projects that have on-paper allowed the opportunity for countries to ease their industrial transition. The Standard Gauge Railway in Kenya, the Addis Ababa-Djibouti Railway in the Horn of Africa, and the development of Abuja’s Rail Mass Transit System in Nigeria all prove a willingness by China to improve African transportation infrastructure.⁶⁷⁸ China has also invested in dams in Sudan, bridges in Mozambique, and expressways in Algeria, so the BRI is viewed by many as giving Africa the chance to catch up to the world.⁹¹⁰¹¹¹² All this, though, has come at a cost.

The Debt Trap and Economic Instability

Economists have been sounding the alarm for years, warning that Chinese loan financing does not produce independence nor development in countries that need both.¹³ Rather, there is growing evidence since the BRI’s launch that the project saddles countries with debt, with little to no positive material impact for the recipient country. Brahma Chellaney of Project Syndicate wrote in January 2017 to this end; arguing that the Initiative was designed to “use economic tools to advance their country’s [China’s] interests”, directly contradicting the CCP narrative.¹⁴

⁵ PR Newswire, “African Union Representative to China: BRI Is a Win-Win Cooperation, Not a Charity,” *PR Newswire*, August 30, 2023, <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/african-union-representative-to-china-bri-is-a-win-win-cooperation-not-a-charity-301955888.html>.

⁶ Wilson Center, “Kenya’s Standard Gauge Railway: The Promise and Risks of Rail Megaprojects,” *Wilson Center*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.wilsoncenter.org/blog-post/kenyas-standard-gauge-railway-the-promise-and-risks-of-rail-megaprojects>.

⁷ Global Infrastructure Hub, “Addis Ababa-Djibouti Railway,” *Global Infrastructure Hub*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.gihub.org/connectivity-across-borders/case-studies/addis-ababa-djibouti-railway/>.

⁸ Daily Trust, “What Residents Should Know About Abuja Rail Mass Transit,” *Daily Trust*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://dailytrust.com/what-residents-should-know-about-abuja-rail-mass-transit/>.

⁹ Sudan Tribune, “Sudan’s Infrastructure Projects and Economic Implications,” *Sudan Tribune*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://sudantribune.com/article34462/>.

¹⁰ Xinhua News, “China’s Role in Africa’s Development Projects,” *Xinhua News*, July 17, 2019, http://www.xinhuanet.com/english/2019-07/17/c_138232354.htm.

¹¹ Xinhua News, “Belt and Road Progress in Africa,” *Xinhua News*, August 13, 2023, <https://english.news.cn/africa/20230813/65019ea47ba24121b241f2dba7fe0801/c.html>.

¹² Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, “How Is China’s Economic Transition Affecting Its Relations with Africa?,” *Carnegie Endowment for International Peace*, May 2024, <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2024/05/how-is-chinas-economic-transition-affecting-its-relations-with-africa?lang=en>.

¹³ Brahma Chellaney, “China’s One Belt One Road Loans: A Debt Trap?,” *Project Syndicate*, January 2017, <https://www.project-syndicate.org/commentary/china-one-belt-one-road-loans-debt-by-brahma-chellaney-2017-01>.

¹⁴ Chatham House, “What Is China’s Belt and Road Initiative (BRI)?,” *Chatham House*, September 2021, <https://www.chathamhouse.org/2021/09/what-chinas-belt-and-road-initiative-bri>.

The Belt and Road program runs under the condition that China loans money to a country to finance the construction of key infrastructure.¹⁵ After a period agreed upon between the local government and the company, the country in question will repay the loan with the anticipated profits. The Chinese method has dramatically outpaced USAID in popularity across Africa, with larger checks, faster project implementation, and more concentrated focus on economic expansion over social governance. Innocent enough, but the African continent is littered with dozens of countries teetering on the edge of economic collapse because of their BRI deals.

In Kenya, BRI involvement has directly led to protests in the capital city of Nairobi in recent months. After a series of ambitious projects, public debt rose to \$80 billion, with the debt-to-GDP ratio far over the IMF recommendation.¹⁶ Facing economic collapse, William Ruto was elected as President in 2022 to reduce dependency on China.¹⁸

Seen as the only way to reduce the national debt, Ruto sought to prevent further pressure from China and the IMF by heavily raising taxes on citizens with his Finance Bill, despite extreme pressure from young Kenyans.¹⁹ Over the summer, however, Ruto was forced to reject the bill after weeks of protests and 400 young Kenyans dead and injured on the streets of Nairobi.²⁰

China's Strategic Interests Over True Partnership

In response, the Kenyan Government was forced to cut roughly the equivalent of USD 3 billion in government services, limiting funding toward county governments across the board to account for the loss of revenue.²¹ Meanwhile, China waits on billions of dollars due by 2025 that, if unpaid in full and on time, many believe could lead to the seizure of the

¹⁵ Statista, "Cumulative Public Debt in Kenya," *Statista*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1223172/cumulative-public-debt-in-kenya/>.

¹⁶ International Monetary Fund (IMF), "IMF-World Bank Debt Sustainability Framework for Low-Income Countries," *IMF*, 2023, <https://www.imf.org/en/About/Factsheets/Sheets/2023/imf-world-bank-debt-sustainability-framework-for-low-income-countries>.

¹⁷ The East African, "Top 10 Foreign Policies for Kenya's New President William Ruto," *The East African*, September 2022, <https://www.theeastafrican.co.ke/tea/news/east-africa/top-10-foreign-policies-for-kenya-new-president-william-ruto-3948384>.

¹⁸ Context, "Why Has Kenya's Finance Bill Triggered Public Outrage?," *Context*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.context.news/money-power-people/why-has-kenyas-finance-bill-triggered-public-outrage>.

¹⁹ CNN, "Kenyan President Rejects Finance Bill," *CNN*, June 26, 2024, <https://www.cnn.com/2024/06/26/africa/kenyan-president-rejects-finance-bill-intl/index.html>.

²⁰ BBC, "Kenya's Economic Struggles and Debt Crisis," *BBC News*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/c9r37wzpw1do>.

²¹ BBC News, "Kenya's Economic Struggles and Debt Crisis," *BBC News*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/c9r37wzpw1do>.

Mombasa Port, forcing Kenya into an unfavorable position where it would seem one step forward brings them two steps back.²²

But this lies at the heart of the problem with the BRI and Chinese-funded development projects more broadly. After speaking with Hudson Institute's Senior Fellow on Africa Joshua Meservey, he argued that the BRI is built on a shaky foundation of cognitive dissonance.

"These problems hurt its image on the continent when so frequently, they talk about win-win cooperation and brotherhood going back to the liberation struggles and also when they demand to get paid," he said.

China toes a fine line between partnership and strategic interests, which do not always align. For decades, they have developed friendships, but it would be naive to think this was out of kindness alone. According to Meservey, "China wants to get paid, fundamentally", and this shapes much of their Africa policy. For example, China does not care about the people of the Congo, but rather the lithium, cobalt, and other minerals the region offers. The January 2024 Sicominex deal with President of the DRC Felix Tshisekedi solidified this fact.²³

China's not bringing anything new of value to the continent. For example, China builds railways and highways from resource-rich areas of the interior to the ports so they can ship minerals out rather than promote self-sufficient regional trade. China mines countries for resources but does not authorize nearly enough processing and refinement plants to provide any value-add en masse there.²⁴ And remarkably, even as bilateral trade volume between China and the continent has increased by a factor of 28 since 2000, GDP per capita at the same time has only increased from \$1,458 in 2000 to \$2,273 in 2023.²⁵

China builds airports but refuses to facilitate social programs that will stimulate wealth among local people to afford air travel. China authorizes the construction of schools, but only so they can shape the next generation of African leaders. China refused to hire local people, despite a continent-wide unemployment crisis, and when they finally did hire

²² The Conversation, "Kenya Could Run Out of Money to Repay Massive Debts," *The Conversation*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://theconversation.com/kenya-could-run-out-of-money-to-repay-massive-debts-how-to-avoid-this-237044>.

²³ Black Agenda Report, "China in Congo: Economic and Political Implications," *Black Agenda Report*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.blackagendareport.com/china-congo>.

²⁴ Wilson Center, "Examining China's Impact on Mining in Africa," *Wilson Center*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.wilsoncenter.org/blog-post/examining-chinas-impact-mining-africa-critiques-and-credible-responses>.

²⁵ Statista, "GDP per Capita in Africa," *Statista*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1300864/gdp-value-per-capita-in-africa/>.

them, they committed gross human rights violations.²⁶ Despite the propaganda, they are as bad or worse than today's West.²⁷ China does not want independence, they want vassals.

The US Opportunity to Counter China

This mix of factors leads to Africa becoming a very politically combustible region in the coming years, and Howard University's Dr. Phiwokuhle Mnyandu, expert on China-Africa relations, believes America is in a prime position to counter.

The BRI is a primarily economic and political project, but the cultural aspect is neglected. With skepticism toward China increasing across the continent, the US can finally leverage these concerns for an ideal marriage of interest between both parties, where the US can undermine its main adversary while African countries are respected as key players in global politics. Given past grievances, rolling back Chinese influence will involve accessing the US' hidden strength in full force for the first time in its history, where the African diaspora will play a crucial role.²⁸

"America gets to now govern in essence a new African Renaissance culturally, and that's a big deal," Mnyandu remarked.

It can already be seen today, as the US Government invests heavily on engaging young black Americans for an entirely new Afro-centric foreign policy, rethinking the way it communicates with the African continent.

In September 2023, for example, President Joe Biden announced the PAC-ADE, granting the platform for black community leaders to "provide invaluable guidance to reinforce cultural, social, political, and economic ties between the U.S. and Africa," promoting trade, investment, and educational exchange. Across the board, America is rethinking how to communicate with the African continent, with HBCUs like Howard University being especially targeted.

Howard's invitation to programs like the Department of State's Foreign Language Area Studies (FLAS) and Academic Centers for Conflict Anticipation and Prevention (ACCAP)

²⁶ Congressional-Executive Commission on China, "China's Exploitation of Labor in the Congo," *Congressional-Executive Commission on China*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.cecc.gov/events/hearings/from-cobalt-to-cars-how-china-exploits-child-and-forced-labor-in-the-congo>.

²⁷ Carnegie Endowment, "How Is China's Economic Transition Affecting Africa?," *Carnegie Endowment for International Peace*, May 2024, <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2024/05/how-is-chinas-economic-transition-affecting-its-relations-with-africa?lang=en>.

²⁸ Wilson Center, "The Role of the Diaspora in Shaping US Policies Toward Africa," *Wilson Center*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.wilsoncenter.org/event/the-role-the-diaspora-shaping-us-policies-toward-africa>.

initiative is telling.²⁹³⁰ Additionally, when the Department of Defense established the Air Force University Research Center (AURC), the Director of National Intelligence established a Center of Excellence for students aspiring to work in the Intelligence Community (IC), and direct admissions for master's programs like Johns Hopkins School of Advanced International Studies, it was no accident, but rather built to engage the diaspora and usher in the next generation of black thought leaders.³¹³²³³

Because until recently, US foreign policy in Africa has been lost. The US began its relationship with today's Africa by promoting and often forcing independence in the early years after World War II, but it attempted to ride the line of its European partnerships, becoming complicit in some of the modern world's greatest violations of international law.³⁴³⁵³⁶³⁷³⁸

U.S. Foreign Aid and the Power of Messaging

Contrarily, the Peace Corps and USAID's contributions have been criminally overlooked. At this year's China Forum hosted by the Victims of Communism Memorial Foundation, Former US Ambassador to the UN's Economic and Social Council and Senior Fellow of the Atlantic Council, Kelley E. Currie, strongly defended US policy of foreign aid, arguing that "[T]he idea that the United States is not committing sufficient resources to what we're doing globally is frankly nonsense.³⁹ We have put plenty of money into these things. We

²⁹ Howard University, "Foreign Language Area Studies (FLAS)," *Howard University Center for African Studies*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://cfas.howard.edu/FLAS>.

³⁰ U.S. Department of State, "Bureau of Conflict and Stabilization Operations Launches Academic Initiative to Anticipate Conflict," *U.S. Department of State*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.state.gov/bureau-of-conflict-and-stabilization-operations-launches-academic-initiative-to-anticipate-conflict/>.

³¹ Howard University, "Howard University Joins Office of Intelligence Community Centers for Academic Excellence Program," *The Dig*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://thedig.howard.edu/all-stories/howard-university-joins-office-intelligence-community-centers-academic-excellence-program-office>.

³² Johns Hopkins School of Advanced International Studies, "Collaborating for Excellence," *Johns Hopkins SAIS*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://sais.jhu.edu/admissions-aid/collaborating-for-excellence#:~:text=Johns%20Hopkins%20SAIS%20offers%20a,well%20as%20select%20concentrations%20in>.

³³ <https://thedig.howard.edu/all-stories/howard-university-awarded-90-million-contract-air-force-dod-establish-first-ever-university>

³⁴ U.S. Department of State, "The Atlantic Charter and the Post-WWII World," *Office of the Historian*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://history.state.gov/milestones/1937-1945/atlantic-conf>.

³⁵ Covert Action Magazine, "This Man Pulled the Trigger: CIA and DGSE Involvement?," *Covert Action Magazine*, April 29, 2022, <https://covertactionmagazine.com/2022/04/29/this-man-pulled-the-trigger-but-did-the-cia-and-dgse-put-the-idea-in-his-head-and-the-gun-in-his-hand/>.

³⁶ U.S. Department of State, "Congo and the Decolonization Process," *Office of the Historian*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://history.state.gov/milestones/1961-1968/congo-decolonization>.

³⁷ Brookings Institution, "Algeria and America: A Complicated Past, an Uncertain Future," *Brookings Institution*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/algeria-and-america-a-complicated-past-an-uncertain-future/>.

³⁸ Sammie Floyd, "African Diaspora's Role in U.S.-Africa Policy," *Menlo School Research Paper*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.menloschool.org/live/files/3479-sammie-floyd.pdf>.

³⁹ YouTube, "Analysis of Africa's Geopolitical Landscape," *YouTube Video*, accessed February 3, 2025, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xbu_g9KKL8U.

contribute \$18 billion annually to the UN system across all channels. China puts in a fraction of that.”

Currie believes it is a matter of messaging, that “[I]t’s what we do with those contributions that matter. If you think about PEPFAR, and the billions of dollars we’ve spent on global health,” rightly claiming that US partners across the continent take foreign aid for granted.

Mnyandu highlights this particularly, “That’s why I’m against those people saying, ‘America needs to do more’, because America is already doing a bunch. It’s just the Peace Corps are told to keep their heads down, don’t be showy, but the Chinese walk there and make sure they let the people know they are there by the grace of the Chinese people”, which fuels the notion that the US isn’t even there, but it is.

It’s for this reason, Currie believes that “[W]e show up to these countries and they’re like, ‘what have you done for me lately?’, and we’re like, ‘well, you know, we just saved a quarter of your population from dying from AIDS, was that ok? Did we do the right thing there?’ We don’t actually remind people of what we are doing. It operates in the background, almost silently, and so we have got to do a better job of making people realize that the United States does contribute to these global public goods in meaningful ways that Beijing does not.”

The Importance of Respect in U.S.-Africa Relations

And it is also about respect. US presidents historically do not visit Africa, and Biden hasn’t gone once.⁴⁰ Even when rarely a President does meet with African leaders, deep within the protection of the White House, it is in groups.⁴¹ In China, however, they are treated as peers.

“The last presidential summit, African leaders complained, because only four or five of them met with the US President bilaterally. The rest of them gathered for photos. When they went to China last month, what happened? Every single one, even a country with only a five-person population, was treated like a VIP. African countries have an inferiority complex about these things, they remember how painful it is to be undermined,” Mnyandu describes.

Any US counter, therefore, must account for these on-the-surface vein things, because they have an enormous impact on politics. So, as the Belt and Road Initiative is increasingly pressured, and this new Scramble for Africa emerges, the US can create a new, more

⁴⁰ Deutsche Welle (DW), “Harris or Trump? Will America’s Africa Strategy Change Under the Next U.S. President?,” *DW News*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.dw.com/en/harris-or-trump-will-americas-africa-strategy-change-under-the-next-us-president/a-70574499>.

⁴¹ U.S. Department of State, “U.S.-Africa Leaders Summit,” *U.S. Department of State*, accessed February 3, 2025, <https://www.state.gov/africasummit/>.

equitable moral standard in its relationship with the continent that leverages existing strengths and untapped resources.

The Path Forward: A New Afro-Centric Foreign Policy

Through an emphasis on respect, partnership, and cultural diplomacy, Howard can lead in America's vocal campaign for peace, freedom, prosperity, and development, providing an authentic alternative to the Chinese model.

For this, the African diaspora is needed. In this truly postcolonial African reality, African Americans can no longer protest policy from the outside but work to fix it from within to bring about a better future for black people with a new Afro-centric US foreign policy. So, fellow Bison, let them see us.